

Socioeconomic issues faced by eunuchs living in Jamshoro: A Sociological Analysis

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Abstract

This study is about socio economic issues of eunuchs. There are several economic and social issues faced by eunuchs such as lack of ethical economic opportunities and lack of education. Majority of eunuchs are forced to earn through unethical works such as prostitution or sex work, dance at functions and begging. Due to lack of income generating opportunities, social class of eunuchs is low and there is no social and cultural acceptance for eunuchs in society. This study is quantitative study and primary method of research was used and this study is descriptive in nature. Researcher used structured interview using closed ended questions to collect data and questionnaire was translated in native language of respondent. Chi square test of independence was used to analyze the data and hypotheses were tested using SPSS version 20.

Keywords: Socioeconomic, begging, economic opportunities.

1. Introduction

Eunuchs, also known as hijras, are a marginalized group in many parts of the world, including in Pakistan. In the city of Jamshoro, eunuchs face a range of socioeconomic issues due to their marginalized status. These issues include poverty, lack of access to education and employment opportunities, and discrimination. A sociological analysis of these issues can provide insight into the ways in which social structures and cultural attitudes contribute to the marginalization of eunuchs in Jamshoro and other similar communities. Such analysis can also help identify potential solutions to these issues.

This study focuses on Eunuchs, sometimes commonly referred to as transgender individuals, in order to investigate the social and economic challenges that they confront. A person who does not adhere to binary gender criteria is referred to as a eunuch, and it is believed that they are unable to live a "normal" life (Abbas, Ali & Nawaz, 2014). In Pakistan, the economic situation of eunuchs is highly precarious; the majority of them are forced to depend on

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beggary, sex labor, and performing at social gatherings in order to make ends meet. The purpose of this study is to examine the socioeconomic issues faced by eunuchs living in Jamshoro, Pakistan, and to understand how these issues are shaped by larger social and cultural factors. The study will use a sociological perspective to explore the ways in which eunuchs experience poverty, lack of access to education and employment, and discrimination, and how these experiences are shaped by their status as a marginalized group in society. The study will also investigate the social and economic resources that eunuchs use to cope with these challenges and the strategies that they employ to improve their socioeconomic status. It is expected that this study will help to shed light on the ways in which eunuchs are affected by poverty and discrimination in Jamshoro, and will provide insights into the social and cultural factors that contribute to these issues. It may also suggest potential solutions that can be implemented to improve the socioeconomic status of eunuchs in this community, and more generally in Pakistan and other similar communities across the world.

1.2 History

Before British rule in subcontinent, eunuchs used to live life of honor and they were part of many important institutions in Mughal Period (Jami,2005) In 1870, eunuchs lost their human rights and conditions are still same (Abbas, Ali & Nawaz, 2014).

1.3 Economic and Social Problems

There are numerous problems faced by eunuchs but economic or financial problem is the most important one as it directly affects their life. Eunuchs are bound to beg or get involved into sex work and even dance at functions as no respectable income generating opportunity is provided to them by society and culture as a whole. They are deprived of education and due to illiteracy they are not able to get respectable jobs.

1.3.1 Education

In this study, education means different levels of education such as illiterate, primary, middle, graduation and so on.

1.3.2 Occupation of eunuchs

In this study, Occupation means the current work eunuchs do to earn.

1.3.3 Social Class

In this study, social class means the financial ladder divided into three levels i.e. upper, middle and lower class.

1.3.4 Low economic condition

In this study, low economic condition means low income i.e. in between 5000 to 10000 rupees per month.

2. Objectives

1. To explore the Economic Problems faced by eunuchs.
2. To find out the impact of Occupation on Social Class of eunuchs.

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3. Review of Literature

Eunuchs living in Pakistan usually are deprived of basic human rights and they face extreme economic issues. Many eunuchs are not able to earn an amount important for their survival. Society’s stereotypes limited eunuchs to unethical ways of earning such as prostitution, dance and begging (Akhtar, 2016).

Above fifty percent of transgenders in KPK, Pakistan is bound to earn through sex work and beggary. Many eunuchs live far away from their actual home as they are ashamed to earn through such unethical works. Transgenders are ready to leave these kinds of works; all they need is support from Government and respect from society (Nazir & Yasir, 2017). Supreme Court of Pakistan focused on Trans gender’s right to work and ordered to provide them employment yet they are unemployed (Amna Nasir, 2013). Eunuchs are facing worst circumstances in all fields of life such as social and economic, the only option left for them to earn is sex work and begging.

4. Research Methodology

The present research is a quantitative study that employs a structured interview method for data collection. The structured interview method involves the use of closed-ended questions, which were administered to all transgenders living in the four tehsils of Jamshoro. The unit of analysis for this study includes all transgenders residing in these four tehsils, as reported by the 2017 census. A total of 44 eunuchs were reported to be living in Jamshoro. The data collected through the structured interview was analyzed using the chi-square test of independence, which was conducted using SPSS version 20. The chi-square test was used to examine the independence of the variables under investigation and test for any significant associations between them.

5. Data Results and Interpretations

Table 1 presents the frequency table highlighting the population characteristics, mainly demographics of the sample. The results show that 31.8% of the population holds primary level education whereas the rest of the sample remains uneducated. The above table shows that majority of transgenders are illiterate. Monthly income of 63.6% of eunuchs is in between 10001 to 15000. They are deprived of earning opportunities as 72.7 % percent said no when asked about income opportunities. The majority i.e. 56.8% replied dance and 43.2% answered begging when asked about their occupation. All of the respondents replied no, they never felt any importance of their existence and they were not satisfied with what they are earning. The Majority i.e. 70.5% said they belong to very low social class.

**Table 1
Frequency Table**

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Category 1</i>	<i>Category 2</i>
Level of Education	31.8% (Primary level)	68.2% (Uneducated)
Monthly Income	36.4% (5000 to 10000)	63.6% (10001 to 15000)
Earning Opportunities	27.3% (Yes)	72.7% (No)
Eunuch’s Current Work	43.2% (Begging)	56.8% (Dance)
Forced to Work	20.5% (No)	79.5% (Yes)

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Feeling of being important	0% (Yes)	100% (No)
Satisfied with monthly income	0% (Yes)	100% (No)
Social Class	29.5% (Middle)	70.5% (Lower)

5.1 Hypotheses Testing

The present study posits two hypotheses, each of them have been dissected below. The findings for the analyses are reflected in tables 2-4.

Hypothesis 1:

Ho: “There is no relationship between education of eunuchs and low economic condition”

H1: “There is a relationship between education of eunuch and low economic condition”

Test: Chi Square test of independence

Degree of freedom: 1

Significant value is 0.05

Table 2
Cross tabulation between Education and Monthly Income

			Monthly Income		Total
			5000 to 10000	10001 to 15000	
Education	Primary	Result	(11f)	(3f)	(14f)
		Estimated Result	(5.1f)	(8.9f)	(14.0f)
	Illiterate	Result	(5f)	(25f)	(30f)
		Estimated Result	(10.9f)	(19.1f)	(30.0f)
Total	Result	(16f)	(28f)	(44f)	
	Expected Result	(16.0f)	(28.0f)	(44.0f)	

Table 3
Chi Square

	(Value)	(DF)	(Asp. Sig) (2-sided)	(Exact Sig) (2-sided)	(Exact Sig) (1-sided)
(Pearson’s Chi Square)	15.808 ^a	1	.000		
(Continuity Correction)	13.246	1	.000		
(Like LaHood-Ratio)	16.100	1	.000		
(Fisher Exact-Test)				.000	.000
(Linear by Linear Association)	15.449	1	.000		
(Valid Cases)	44				

The Null hypothesis is rejected because the probability value .000 is less than the significant value 0.05. Further the computed value 15.808 is greater than the tabulated value 3.84.

Hypothesis 2:

Ho: “There is no relationship between Occupation of eunuchs and Social Class”

H1: “There is a relationship between Occupation of eunuchs and Social Class”

Test: Chi Square test of Independence

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Freedom Degree: 1
 Significant Value is 0.05

Table 4
Cross tabulation between Occupation of eunuchs and Social Class

		Result	Social Class		Total
			Middle	low	
Occupation	Begging	Result	9f	10f	19f
		Estimated Result	5.6f	13.4f	19.0f
	Dancing at functions	Result	4f	21f	25f
		Estimated Result	7.4f	17.6f	25.0f
Total	Result	13f	31f	44f	
	Estimated Result	13.0f	31.0f	44.0f	

Table 5
Chi Square

	(Value)	(DF)	(Asp. Sig) (2-sided)	(Exact Sig) (2-sided)	(Exact Sig) (1-sided)
(Pearson's Chi Square)	5.103 ^a	1	.024		
(Continuity Correction)	3.707	1	.054		
(Likelihood-Ratio)	5.142	1	.023		
(Fisher Exact-Test)				.044	.027
(Linear by Linear Association)	4.987	1	.026		
(Valid Cases)	44				

The null hypothesis is rejected because the probability value .024 is less than the significant value 0.05. Further the computed value 5.103 is greater than the tabulated value 3.84.

6. Conclusion

The results conclude this study as there is absolutely no doubt that eunuchs are not living in good conditions. They are facing several economic and social issues. The impact of lack of education on their low income is huge and the options provided by the society and culture to earn are unethical and directly they are forced to earn through begging and sex work. Cultural acceptance for eunuchs is almost zero. Further there is a relation of occupation of eunuch with their social class.

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7. Recommendations

It is crucial for society to begin accepting eunuchs as an integral part of their culture and community. This can be achieved through education and awareness programs that aim to break down stereotypes and prejudices. The government also has an important role to play in this regard. They should provide eunuchs with all basic human rights, such as the right to education, employment, and freedom of speech. This will empower them and enable them to participate fully in society. Additionally, the government should take steps to ensure the safety and security of eunuchs. This includes making laws that prevent families from abandoning their children on the basis of their gender. Furthermore, Awareness campaigns should be organized to inform the public about the third gender and the issues they face. These programs will help create a more inclusive and understanding society, where eunuchs are treated with the respect and dignity they deserve.

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